

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

EXTENSION OF IMPERSONAL SIMPLE SENTENCES IN AZERBAIJANI AND FRENCH LANGUAGES

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Abstract

The article mainly deals with the extension forms of personal simple sentences in Azerbaijani and French languages. A speaker of both languages can present his/her opinion by means of unextended or extended, complete or incomplete, indefinite personal or general personal, impersonal or nominal sentences. In the mentioned languages, there are also facts of extension of the impersonal simple sentence, and this process appears in all types of impersonal sentences. It undergoes extension in an impersonal sentence consisting of only one word. In the extension of sentences whose predicate is expressed by the impersonal form of the verb, the main burden falls on secondary members. In French, verbs that are used only in the third person singular and sometimes with the pronoun 'ce' are called impersonal verbs. 'Il' or 'ce' is used as a grammatical sign, i.e. formally, and does not represent any person or thing. Complements of this type are often used after transitive verbs. However, complements of impersonal verbs are also found after intransitive verbs. The extension of impersonal verbs is expressed by pronoun, quantity, infinitive, substantive word and noun.

Keywords: extension, simple sentence, extended sentence, complex sentence, unextended

In the Azerbaijani and French languages, simple sentences can be extended by various means. These possibilities can be realized both with members and with morphological means that cannot play the role of members. The complex structure of sentence members increases the possibilities of sentence extension. "In linguistics, many of the controversial issues related to the means of extending a simple sentence have not yet been resolved" [5, p. 346].

Most of the tools in question cannot function as sentence members, but nevertheless justify the structural-semantic completion of the sentence. It is interesting that the concept of "extension" refers to a simple sentence. "Extended sentences are essentially a transition between simple sentences and complex sentences. Although such sentences approach a complex sentence due to the quantitative increase of predication possibilities, they remain a simple sentence type because the quantitative change cannot be transferred to quality" [5, p.346].

In both Azerbaijani and French languages, a simple sentence attracts attention as a syntactic unit with an active position. As for the types of simple sentences, their expression is related to the speech culture and vocabulary of those who express their thoughts. In this process, the culture of thinking of the speaker, his attitude towards the object and events in question, and the situation of the speech are also important. The speaker is independent in presenting his opinion by means of unextended or extended, complete or incomplete, indefinite personal or general personal, impersonal or nominal sentences. It is true that some of these signs (for example, completeness or incompleteness) can also be present in complex sentences. However, in the linguistic reference, the concepts of completeness and incompleteness are mainly associated with simple sen-

tence syntax. This is how impersonal sentences are explained in the modern Azerbaijani language book [1]. "Impersonal sentences are also a type of single-component sentences. It is necessary to consider the sentences that have no subject and cannot be imagined as personal".

Impersonal sentences in Azerbaijani language can be divided into two parts according to the expression of the predicate and the part of speech: 1) impersonal sentences with a noun 2) impersonal sentences with a verb. [3. p.266]

In the mentioned languages, there are also facts of extension of the impersonal simple sentence, and this work can occur in all types of impersonal sentences. Let's look at the impersonal sentence consisting of only the word and its extension: *Səhərdir – Aydın səhərdir – İşıqlı və aydın səhərdir. İndi işıqlı və aydın səhərdir.* The following example is interesting as a fact of extension of an impersonal sentence consisting of word combinations:

Novruz bayramı idi – Çoxdan gözlədiyimiz Novruz bayramı idi – Çoxdan gözlədiyimiz sevimli Novruz bayramı idi – Çoxdan gözlədiyimiz ruhumuzu oxşayan əziz Novruz bayramı idi.

Payızın ilk günü idi – Soyuq payızın ilk günü idi – Yayın axırından özünü göstərən soyuq payızın ilk günü idi.

In the extension of the sentence whose predicate is expressed by the impersonal form of the verb, the main burden falls on the secondary members: *Baxıldı – Sənədlərə baxıldı – Hazırlanmış sənədlərə baxıldı – Dünəndən hazırlanmış sənədlərə baxıldı – Dünəndən hazırlanmış bu sənədlərə baxıldı – Dünəndən hazırlanmış bu sənədlərə diqqətlə baxıldı.*

İşlərə fikir verilmir – Belə işlərə fikir verilmir – İndi belə işlərə fikir verilmir – İndi hamını narahat

edən belə işlərə fikir verilmir – İndi hamını narahat edən belə işlərə o qədər də fikir verilmir

Studies show that it is possible to extend impersonal sentences expressed by phraseological combinations in Azerbaijani: Gözüm su içmir – Gözüm səndən su içmir – İndi gözüm səndən su içmir – İndi mənim gözüm səndən su içmir və s.

Ürəyim düşdü – Qorxudan ürəyim düşdü – Birdən-birə qorxudan ürəyim düşdü – Qapı açılarda birdən-birə qorxudan ürəyim düşdü – Qapı qəflətən açılarda birdən-birə qorxudan ürəyim düşdü – Qapı qəflətən möhkəm açılarda birdən-birə qorxudan ürəyim düşdü və s.

In French, verbs that are used only in the third person singular and sometimes with the pronoun *ce* are called impersonal verbs. 'Il' or 'ce' is used as a grammatical sign, i.e. formally, and does not represent any person or thing.

Many personalized verbs are also close to these constructions, so they are called similar constructions.

In modern French, only one verb - the verb *falloir* - is used only in the impersonal form. Other verbs can be used in both personal and impersonal forms. Such verbs mainly include verbs denoting natural phenomena: *il pleut, il neige, il grêle, il bruine, il tonne*

When these verbs are used in the personal form, their subject is expressed by a noun, and the construction has a figurative meaning: *Boulets, mitraille, obus, mêlés aux flocons blancs pleuvaient. La lune neige sa lumière sur la couronne gothique de la tour du tombeau de Métella.*

Other verbs that are normally used in all persons are also often used in the impersonal form. For example, *Məs* : *L'eau gèle à 0. Su sifir dərəcədə donur.*

Nous gelons dans cette salle mal chauffée. Biz zəif qızdırılmış bu otaqda donuruq.

Il gèle aujourd'hui. Bu gün şaxtadır.

From this point of view, impersonal verbs in French are divided into three groups:

1. The most basic of the impersonal verbs that are always used more frequently are:

The verb 'avoir' is used to show whether things or people are in a place. Personal verbs such as *arriver* - to arrive, *advenir* - to happen are also used as impersonal verbs when possible.

- *Qu'est-il donc arrivé? Demanda le professeur*

- *Il arriva que la guerre a éclaté.*

- *Il advient un jour que cette rue si triste, ... il advient que cette rue est pleine des enfants*

2. Être – the verb to be shows the existence of any thing:

Il était un petit navire.

Il est aux bois des fleurs sauvages.

The verb 'être' takes the impersonal form when expressing time relations: *Il est 3 heures, Il est midi, minuit, Il est tôt, tard.*

3. The verb 'Être' has an impersonal meaning when combined with an adjective to express reasoning: *Il est bon, il est juste, vrai, rare, évident, difficile, possible, nécessaire* və s. :

Il est possible qu'il vienne.

The verb 'faire', used with an adjective, noun, without an article, or with an article denoting a part, which

expresses natural phenomena, also has an impersonal form: *Il fait froid, chaud, frais ; il fait clair, sombre ; il fait bon, beau, mauvais* və s.; *il fait (du) soleil, du vent, il fait nuit.*

Il faisait, ce jour-là, très froid. Il faisait nuit quand cet accident est arrivé.

The verbs 'plaire', 'paraître', 'sembler', 'convenir', 'suffire', 'se trouver' can also be used in an impersonal sense and can be extended with infinitives that follow them, as well as with clauses connected with the conjunction 'que'.

Verbs such as *dire, répondre, prouver, décider, résoudre, permettre, défendre, interdire*, which are used as transitive verbs, can be presented as impersonal verbs in the passive form if they do not specify or cannot specify the doer of the action. For example,

Il est interdit de fumer dans ce taxi.

Il est défendu de marcher sur les pelouses.

Il est permis de stationner pendant deux heures.

Il a été décidé de fermer ce musée.

Reflexive verbs, which have an intransitive or reflexive meaning, can be used in the impersonal form accompanied by a noun, even if they do not have the reflexive meaning.

Some of these verbs are more typical of spoken language. Verbs such as *arriver, manquer, and rester* are of this type.

Arriver - baş vermək, vaxt olmaq :

Il est arrivé un malheur (un malheur est arrivé.

Il m'est arriva dans cette chambre des aventures extraordinaires (A. France)

Manquer - çatmamaq, çatışmaz olmaq, əldən buraxmaq : Il manque plusieurs pages dans ce livre. Il y manque l'air.

Rester – qalmaq: Il reste quelques minutes jusqu'au départ du train

Impersonal constructions of this type are widely used in modern French. Impersonal verbs can be extended with indefinite article nouns, indefinite adjectives, numbers, and quantifiers, depending on the meaning of the context within the construction.

Remnants of the Old French language can be found in some phraseological expressions formed by impersonal verbs. Thus, impersonality has preserved its meaning even without the pronoun 'il'.

Impersonal verbs and impersonal expressions, except for impersonal verbs that describe natural phenomena, cannot form a singular sentence with a pronoun. These compounds must always be accompanied by branch clauses that complete them with the conjunction 'que', by infinitives used by the preposition 'de', and by the noun and the real object of the verb.

In the colloquial language, sometimes the pronoun 'ce' and the verb 'être' are not used in these expressions. For example:

On dit que vous allez en France ? – (C'est) possible.

Nous ne pourrions pas aller avec vous. – (C'est) dommage. [4, p.159].

The complement (expansion) of impersonal verbs is used with formal impersonal verbs. This part of the sentence plays the role of semantically, as in the following examples ;

Il se fit un silence coupé de tintements de verres choqués d'une toux nerveuse, du halètement d'un remorqueur qui passait presque sous les fenêtres du restaurant.

Il en existe une excellente édition scolaire, publiée, avec note et appendice, par le professeur Ah Tchou, de Pékin.

Complements of this type are often used after transitive verbs. However, complements of impersonal verbs are also found after intransitive verbs. Complements of impersonal verbs are expressed by the following grammatical means:

- With pronouns : *Il y en a dans chaque maison.*

- With Indefinite numeral : *J'ai compté, dit-elle, il y en avait dix-neuf avec celui-là.*

- With Infinitive : *En tout cas, vaut mieux éviter les chemins et le découvert.*

- With substantivized word : *Après il ne restera guère de vivants ici.*

- With noun: *Il y a des fossées profonds, avec la neige on ne le verra pas.* [2, p. 114]

As a result of the research, impersonal sentence forms were discovered in the Azerbaijani and French

languages, and we witnessed the possibilities of extending these sentences with different forms. Although they do not have a specific person, these sentences extend in the language and serve to convey ideas to the reader in a more complete and meaningful form.

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